

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN THE KARU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF NASARAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study assessed the impact of domestic violence on academic performance among secondary school students in the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. The study employed survey research design. The study population consisted of 26,248 students of public secondary in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa State. Using a random sampling technique, 300 students were selected for the study. A self-constructed questionnaire was used for data collection. The questionnaire drawn for this was subjected to face and content by research, measurement and evaluation experts, and their comments and observations led to the refinement of the instrument for precision. A validity index of 0.92 was obtained. Through pilot testing, a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was established. Descriptive statistics of mean and deviation were used to answer research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested using chi-square statistic at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that physical, social, and psychological violence has a significant impact on secondary school students' academic performance. It was recommended that students should be continually motivated with their educational pursuit and forget about domestic violence. Orientation services should be made available to expose students to the consequences of physical violence. Parents should also be counseled not to subject their children to domestic and psychological violence. Sociologists can also be of assistance to victims of domestic violence by adjusting them to interact freely and participate in every school function.

Keywords: Assessment, Impact, Domestic violence, Academic performance

Introduction

A close observation shows that incidents of domestic violence generally in Nasarawa State and most parts of Nigeria at large has increased to an alarming rate (Nnanchi, 2004). One begins to wonder what is happening to the institution of marriage and family which form the core of many social systems. Ideally, it is every child's dream, irrespective of age and sex, to be surrounded by the reflective love of his or her parents, which is pride among his or her peers a love that radiates from his/her parents' healthy relationship with each other as spouses. Carte (2004) found that offspring are most likely to model their life pattern on what is obtained in the family; as such offspring from violent prone families are most likely to experience neglect and trauma, which can produce measurable changes in the brain function of the child and prevent the offspring from achieving their human potential. Shek et al (1998) opines that a good home is of greatest importance to adolescents. A good home that

provides love, support, encouragement, and security that will enable the individual to cope with life's demands. Therefore, the home is a unit that transmits to the adolescent his or her cultural norms and standards of society and helps the adolescent adjust to the outside world. However, a critical look around us reveals that this dream may not be realized in most homes due to the effects of domestic violence on these adolescents.

Domestic violence refers to the act of threat or the use physical, emotional, or verbal power to intimidate, or physically injure anyone within the family. According to Phares (2004), the last 20 years have been acknowledged as a rapidly growing health and social problem that needs urgent attention and redress worldwide. Thus, it engages all forms of family squabbles, physical combat between parents, parent-children conflict and siblings' bitterness and rivalry. Carte (2004) upholds that domestic violence takes a devastating toll on children and society at large. This implies that adolescents' childhood experiences of victimization through direct violence of any kind, neglect, or witnessing of parental domestic violence have demonstrated long-term consequences for adolescent violence, adult violence and other forms of criminality.

According to Kim et al (2009), human destructiveness is never inborn, and inherited traits are neither good nor evil. How they develop depends on one's character, which is formed in the course of one's life and the nature of which depends in turn on one's experiences, especially in childhood and adolescence, and on the decisions one makes as an adult. It therefore implies that, domestic violence affect the personality of the adolescent, which in turn affects his or her educational achievement in school and in life generally. James (2005) observed that children who experience domestic violence exhibit a variety of behavior and emotional problems ranging from academic difficulties to the approval of violence as a problem-solving method.

By the time children reach adolescence, their cognitive skills and adaptation resources have usually reached a developmental stage that encompasses both their own family dynamics and outside social networks, such as peer groups and school influences. They become aware that there are different ways of thinking, feeling, and acting in the world from those to which they have been exposed (Stephanic, 2007; Uchem, 2008). However, the question is whether the behavioral and social learning processes of adolescents who have been exposed to domestic violence have become so entrenched that they find it difficult to engage in more positive interaction. For instance, Humor et al (2005) and Hodges (2001) concluded that growing up in a violent family increases the likelihood of becoming a violent housewife, while Hughes and Barad (1983) found that a high incidence of violent men and their victims have been raised in violent homes and witnessed domestic violence as children. However, not all children who have lived with abusive relationships will repeat the experience.

Harold et al, (2004) and Lannap (2002) stated that in recent year domestic violence has begun to come out in the open recently. Societies in general are slowly become aware of the rights of children and women. Some parents violence their children, their wives, and even their pregnant wives, which pose a serious risk to both the mother and child. There is a probability that a man who hits his wife will also violently assault his children. Children who suffer domestic violence display some difficulties such as anxiety, depression, social violence, difficulty sleeping, aggressive behavior, and constant worry about possible danger. Domestic violence is one of the most serious and widespread problems in modern society. In the Karu Local Government Area, as in most other societies, domestic violence traditionally has been kept hidden because it is considered a private issue. Faced with this, most victims of violence have no recourse but to feel ashamed and even guilty. Some even suffer from depression and social trauma.

The physical, social, and mental educational attainment of secondary school students depends on a good family background. Thus, a family whose environment is prone to violence is most likely to have its offspring experience some psychological deficiencies, including depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress, and low self-esteem, irrespective of sex and age (Marcus et al, 2001). The psycho-social impact puts the student's academic performance at risk. **Psychological** violence can be defined as the intentional act or collective force against a

person that results in physical, mental, spiritual, moral, and social harm, including insults, threats, attacks, and verbal violence (Ogbuka, 2003). Psychological violence may impact academic performance. The psychological effects of domestic violence on students indicate that they are very likely to affect their academic performance because, according to Paddila (2003), a person's ability to perceive, identify, and manage emotions or moods provides the basis for the kinds of social and emotional competences that are important for success in almost any life engagement or job. A traumatized environment dominated by family violence cannot guarantee offspring's academic achievement. Accordingly, reports have confirmed that the behavior problems of offspring that witness family violence include being aggressive and passive, refusing to go to school, lying to avoid confrontation, rigid defenses, excessive attention seeking, bed wetting and nightmares, reduced intelligence, competencies, dependence, and mood giving (Emery, 1999).

The fear or failure, anxiety, and worry that accompany offspring from violent prone families not only determine their low self-concept and esteem but also deny them the spirit of hard work, which is also the hallmark of academic performance. The absence of hard work equally denies one having appropriate challenges and learning situation for an individual's perception of his/her ability and competence. Unavoidably, however, these characteristics constitute vital portions in determining one's academic performance. Domestic violence incapacitates offspring's ability to understand, evaluate, and manage emotions of self and others. Indeed, violent families are unlikely to produce happy, caring, and optimistic citizens.

Physical violence is an act that attempts to cause or results in pain and physical injury. As with all forms of violence, the main aim of the perpetrator is not only to cause physical pain but, also to limit the other's self-determination. The perpetrator of physical violence sends a clear message to the victim: "I can do things to you that you do not want to happen" Such violence demonstrates differences in social power or may intend to promote particular demands through coercion, sometimes regularly. Physical violence in intimate relationships, often referred to as domestic violence, continues to be a widespread phenomenon in every country.

Physical violence in the private sphere affects young people. As mentioned above, witnessing one parent's violence by another leads to serious psychological harm in children. Often, children and young people who are present during an act of spousal violence will also be injured, sometimes by accident and sometimes because they try to intervene.

Unfortunately, a traumatized social environment dominated by domestic violence, where good attitudes and positive values are to be formed, cannot guarantee the development of an individual's cognitive and psychological domain.

This implies that some violent families cannot provide the needed social and material support to energize the offspring toward improving their self-esteem, self-independence, and achievement motivation at the right age. Accordingly, reports have confirmed that the behavior problems of offspring that witness domestic violence include being aggressive and passive, refusing to go to school, lying to avoid confrontation, rigid defenses, excessive attention seeking, bed wetting, and reduced intelligence, competencies, dependence, and mood giving.

Unavoidably, however, these characteristics constitute vital portions in determining one's social intelligence. The above indicates that favorable biological, social, physical, and psychological environments at home provide a fertile ground for the development of one's social intelligence; unfortunately, a violent family cannot produce such environments. This is because domestic violence incapacitates offspring's ability to understand, evaluate, and manage emotions of self and others. Indeed, violent families are not likely to produce happy, caring, and optimistic citizens.

Social violence is part of every abusive relationship. It makes the victim feel responsible for the actions of their violence and can have extreme negative effects on the victim's sense of self-worth over time. Social violence

may include constant criticism and put downs, "gas lighting", blaming the victim for the violence actions, isolating the victim from their support system and/or the outside world, extreme jealousy and/or accusing the victim of having affairs, demanding the victim "check in" and/or monitoring where they go and who they see and talk to.

Accordingly, Grych (2002) commented that children who witness violent behavior in a family context have high aggression and anxiety, lower self-esteem and self-concept, and a greater incidence of behavioral problems than those who are not exposed to this behavior (violence). In turn, these effects impact their relationship with peers, educational attainment, and mental health.

This shows that students who are domestically violence find it difficult to attain their educational goals. This study investigates the impact of domestic violence on academic performance of public secondary school students in the Local Government Area of Nasarawa State.

Statement of the problem

The researcher has seen several cases of domestic violence in Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, where women are beaten by their husbands, wives insult their husbands, and parents fight with their children. The case culminated into psychological, social, and physical trauma among secondary school students in the study area. The home or domestic environment is the first social organization that children come in contact with. It is a training ground for potential leaders who will eventually take over the affairs of the world. If the children are traumatized from home, then there is no hope for the future. Despite the important functions of the family, it has come under severe threats by the forces of domestic violence. In some families, the forces of divorce have equally inflicted educational, psychological, and social damages on the children, resulting in poor academic performance, especially for secondary school students. This worrisome phenomenon calls for greater concern today, which has caught the attention of researchers. Furthermore, the increasing rate of violence and wanton destruction of lives and property, kidnaping political thuggery, and other forms of delinquency are very likely to originate from children experience of domestic violence. If parents demonstrate good character to their children, most children should be academically well adjusted, warm, genuine, persistent, and optimistic. Instead of developing into responsible, functional, tolerant, happy, and friendly individuals, our children or students are full of aggression, anxiety, depression, annoyance, upsetting memories, distress, and discomfort. All these factors affect their academic performance and makes one to suspect that domestic violence is the probable explanation for all social insecurity and violent crimes; thus, presupposing that violent families be indicted. Therefore, this study intends to determine the outcome of violence in families and the academic performance of students.

Objectives of the study

This study investigates the impact of domestic violence on academic performance of public secondary school students in the Nasarawa State Karu Local Government Area. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Assess the impact of physical violence on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Karu Local Government Area.
- ii. Determine the impact of social violence on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Karu Local Government Area was examined.
- iii. Determine the impact of psychological violence on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Karu Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions were developed to guide this study:

1. What impact does physical violence have on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa State?

2. What impact does social violence have on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa?
3. What impact does psychological violence have on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed and tested at a significance level of 0.05.

Physical violence has no significant impact on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Nasarawa State Karu LGA

Social violence has no significant impact on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Nasarawa State Karu LGA.

Psychological violence has no significant impact on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Nasarawa State Karu LGA.

Methodology

This study employed survey research design, which is suitable for collecting data to describe the characteristics of a given population. The study population consisted of 26,248 students of public secondary schools in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa State. Using a random sampling technique, 300 students were selected for the study. This technique ensured that every member of the population had an equal opportunity to be selected. A self-constructed questionnaire was used for data collection. The questions were divided into two parts, with the first part requesting the respondents to provide personal data. The second part is analytical. The question posed here helps the researcher answer the research questions that guides the study. The response options were based on a 5-point Likert format of SA-Strongly Agree, A – Agree, U-Undecided, D – Disagree, SD- Strongly Disagree with 5 points scale.

The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity by three experts in the field of measurement and evaluation and educational psychology. Based on their observations and comments, the instrument was refined for precision. A validity index of 0.92 was obtained, indicating high content validity. A pilot test was conducted with 35 students outside the main sample to determine reliability and assess the instrument consistency. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the Chronbach’s alpha coefficient, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.78. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested using chi-square statistic at 0.05 level of significance. The mean academic performance levels for decision-making were presented as “accepted”3.00 above and “rejected”3.00 below.

Results

Research Question One: What impact does physical violence have on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of students’ responses on the impact of physical violence on secondary school students’ academic performance.

S/n	item	\bar{X}	STD	Decision
1.	Children who are not well fed cannot concentrate on class			4.39 0.867 Accept
2.	Children who’re overworked with domestic work have no time to read And do assignments	2.03	0.892	Reject
3.	Because parents do not supervise the children’s assignments, they don’t do the following Well in the class		.443	0.892 Accept
4.	Parents who do not provide a conducive reading environment			

cannot read at home so they fail examination

4.40 0.855 Accept

Cluster Mean

3.81 0.62 Accept

The data presented in Table 1 showed that respondents rated all the items 1-4 and prevalence showed a mean score of 3.81, which is well above the cut-off point of 3.00. For items 1-4, the mean scores were 4.39, 2.03, 4.43, and 4.40, respectively, with corresponding standard deviations of 0.87, 0.89, 0.81, and 0.86. The result depicts that physical violence affect students' academic performance. This implies that students who are physically violent performed very poorly in academics.

Research Question Two: What impact does social violence have on the academic performance of public secondary school students in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviations of Student Responses on the Impact of Social Violence on Academic Performance.

S/N	item	\bar{X}	STD	Decision
5.	Children who are not provided with learning materials and their performance are affected by class tests and assignments	4.43	0.795	Accept
6.	Parents' failure to provide seats for their children affects their class performance.	1.93	0.77	Reject
7.	Children who are not allowed to interact with friends during their leisure time cannot speak fluently	4.43	0.82	Accept
8.	Trekking a long distance to school makes children too tired to participate learning activities in the	4.40	0.88	Accept
Cluster mean		3.798	0.603	Accept

Table 2 shows that the mean ratings of respondents for item 5-8 were 4.43, 1.93, 4.43, and 4.40, respectively, with corresponding standard deviations of 0.795, 0.77, 0.82, and 0.88. Based on the cut-off point of 3.00, respondents rated items 5, 7, and 8 as accepted, whereas item 6 was not accepted. This indicates that social violence affects the academic performance of students. This implies that students who are socially violent performed very poorly in academics.

Research Question Three: What impact does psychological violence have on the academic performance of public secondary school students in Nasarawa State' Karu LGA?

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviations of Responses on the Impact of Psychological Violence on Academic Performance.

S/N	item	\bar{X}	STD	Decision
9.	Children are not happy when their parents hate them, which affect their class Participation and performance.	2.00	0.848	Accept
10.	Parents who are always engaged in drinking alcohol and smoking Children are depressed and fail the examination.	4.41	0.819	Accept
11.	Children whose parents curse in the presence of their friends are ashamed in the school and cannot perform well	4.36	0.899	Accept
12.	Because children are always sick, their parents reject them and they cannot Concentrate on class.	4.35	0.931	Accept
Cluster Mean		3.77	0.666	Accept

The results of the analysis of data presented in Table 3 showed that the mean ratings of respondents for item 9-12 were 2.000, 4.41, 4.36, and 4.35, respectively, with corresponding standard deviations of 0.85, 0.82, 0.90,

and 0.93, respectively. Based on the cut-off point of 3.00, respondents rated items 10, 11, and 12 as acceptable, whereas item 9 was not. This shows that psychological violence affects academic performance. This implies that students who are psychologically violent performed very poorly in academics.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One: Physical violence has no significant impact on the academic performance of public secondary school students in Karu LGA.

Table 5: Chi-square analysis of the impact of physical violence on academic performance

Observed	the expected	sig.	Df	X ² cal	X ² crit	Decision
164	71.5	0.05	11	355.10	19.7	rejected
89	71.5					
33	71.5					
11	71.5					

X²cal = 355.10, X²crit =19.7, df =11, P = 0.05 > 0.000

Table 4 shows that the calculated chi-square value of 355.10 is greater than the critical chi-square value of 19.7 checked of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that physical violence has a significant impact on secondary school students’ academic performance.

Hypothesis Two: Social violence has no significant impact on the academic performance of public secondary school students in Karu LGA.

Table 5: Chi-square analysis of the impact of social violence on academic performance

Observed	the expected	sig.	Df	X ² cal	X ² crit	Decision
164	71.5	0.05	11	389.09	18.5	rejected
89	71.5					
33	71.5					
11	71.5					

X²cal = 389.09, X²crit =18.5, df = 11, P=0.05 > 0.000

Table 5 shows that the calculated chi-square value of 389.09 is greater than the critical chi-square value of 18.5 checked at the 0.05 level of significance and 1 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that social violence has a significant impact on secondary school students’ academic performance.

Hypothesis Three: Psychological violence has no significant impact on the academic performance of public secondary school students in Karu LGA.

Table 6: Chi-square analysis of the impact of psychological violence on academic performance

Observed	the expected	sig.	Df	X ² cal	X ² crit	Decision
164	71.5	0.05	11	401.10	23.7	Rejected
89	71.5					
33	71.5					
11	71.5					

X²cal = 401.10, X²crit =23.7 df = 11, P = 0.05 > 0.000

Table 6 shows that the chi-square calculated value of 401.10 is greater than the chi-square critical value of 23.7 checked at the 0.05 level of significance and at 1 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Psychological violence has a significant impact on the academic performance of secondary school students.

Discussion of the Findings

This study was conducted to assess the impact of domestic violence on academic performance of students in the Karu LGA of Nasarawa State. This is because there is an alarming increase in the prevalence of domestic violence, the antecedent of withdrawal from formal education, and the dropout rate of school children within the area, as well as the psychological, social, economic, and health implications on the future of secondary school students within the study area. The findings revealed that physical, social, and psychological violence affects the academic performance of students in the Karu Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. These findings affirmed the findings of Kelly (2000) and Kim et al, (2009) in their studies on the influence of the home environment and domestic violence on students' academic performance. They found that students' home environment and domestic violence affect academic achievement. This implies that students' home environment that is prone to violence performs poorly in academics.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the results and findings of this study, it was concluded that, students perceive domestic violence have significant effects on academic performance. This is because physical, social, and psychological violence have a significant impact on academic performance.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations were made.

- i. Students should be continually motivated with their educational pursuit and forget about domestic violence. Orientation services should be made available to expose students to the consequences of physical violence.
- ii. Educational psychologists and counseling psychotherapist should reach out to students who are prone to social violence and expose them to the dangers of domestic violence and also counsel those who are victims.
- iii. Parents should also be counseled not to subject their children to domestic and psychological violence.
- iv. Sociologists can also be of assistance to victims of domestic violence by adjusting them to interact freely and participate in every school function.

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